

Women Organizations' Activities on Community Development in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of women organisations on community development activities in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated for the study. The population of the study consisted of 10,150 women who are members of women organizations in the Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Through simple random sampling technique a total of 385 respondents were selected for the study. The research instrument used for the study was a questionnaire which was developed by the researchers and which yielded a reliability index of 0.71 and content validity of 0.90. The data generated from the study were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics. The findings revealed that women organisations play active roles in community development activities in the study area. The study recommended that the various governments (local, state and federal) should give matching grants and adequate funding to women organisations that are involved in community development activities.

Keywords: Women; Organisation; Community; Development; Ikwerre; Rivers State; Nigeria

Introduction

Women played significant roles within their families and communities. Their roles are important in economic, social and political areas, as tried to influence government policies on those matters, such as the franchise for women, taxation of women, educational opportunities for girls and property rights and conditions of service for women which determine the status and roles of women in society (Mba, 1997). Okwakpam and Eni (2012) has it that studies by Johnson (1966), Hallet (1965), Mba (1982), Awe (1991) and Denze (1994) asserted that women have been involved in community development programmes since the 19th

century. Since 1950, women have contributed greatly to the development of their communities (Moser, 2010); especially in area of anti-poverty approach or reduction of poverty aimed at improving and advancing women's productivity.

Women are generally keen and enthusiastic to get involved in programmes that will improve their well-being and that of their communities (Akpanam, 2010). Women engage in community building to improve their own lives, those of their families and of the people living around them (Gittell, Ortega-Bustamante and Steff, 1999).

Women have created innovative, comprehensive programmes to meet the needs of their communities. They have established themselves as leaders in the community development field and acquired the skills that have brought positive change to their communities (Gittell, *et. al.*, 1999). They act as volunteers to work for the improvement of their communities. Indeed, they are responsible for development issues of the community only (Deekor and Nnodim, 2005); which them the bedrock of the development of any nation (Ucheagu, 1999).

Women have formed themselves into groups or organisations in order to move the communities forward. Women organisations are inclusive are primarily aimed at helping people within a local community to identify their social needs, to consider the most effective ways of meeting these and to set about doing so, as far as their available resources permit.

Community development activities are being promoted by these women organisations through the construction of feeder roads, provision of social services like deep wells, sinking of bore holes, creation of bus stops and building of waiting sheds; advancement of economic activities through creation of markets; provision of health facilities; creation of efficient agricultural sector, leadership development, neighbourhood revitalization, job training or education, public policy advocacy, child care, mentoring and community organizing.

Women contribution to community development activities in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria has resulted to the formation of many women groups and organizations in the area. In the past, women in the local government area are mostly trusted with child bearing and caring. A women's contribution in a community is greatly related to the number of worthy children she has brought up in the community. With the formation of women organisation, some of the problems affecting them and their communities are addressed collectively, rather than as individuals. This study therefore looks at the roles of women organizations in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria played in community development activities.

Statement of the problem

It is a common and accepted norm in the Nigerian society that, it is the responsibility for government to provide basic amenities for the populace. Government has been trying to provide these amenities to various communities;

which includes the provision of road networks, educational institutions, electricity, and building of markets, among others.

Experience however shows that although government on her part has been trying to provide some forms of amenities to the various communities. Human needs are insatiable and the government alone cannot meet all these needs. More so, the vastness of the local government area conspicuously reveals that the government alone cannot salvage the life of the people nor adequately address the developmental needs of the area.

Hence there is need for the people to form themselves into organisations or associations to articulate their views, identify their felt needs and initiate move towards the realisation of such identified needs. Women have taken greater stride in community development efforts by forming themselves into organisations.

This study therefore seeks to investigate and analyse the roles of women organisations in community development programmes in Ikwerre local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Assessment of the roles hopes to provide possible workable solutions that will encourage more active participation of women organisations in community development activities and bring about improved better living conditions from whatever project they embarked upon. This is the problem which the study addresses upon. And this is the thrust of this study.

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